

An assessment of Disability inclusion in water, sanitation, and hygiene services; a case study of Gulu District, Northern Uganda

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Executive Summary

This report presents the results from a study on disability inclusion in WASH services carried out in four villages of Kal Ali parish, Gulu district Northern Uganda. The study sought to explore the institutional and capacity constraints on the inclusion of people with disability in water, sanitation, and hygiene services in Gulu district, in northern Ugandan.

The overarching questions which this study sought to answer were:

- I. To what extent are people with disability at community level involved in water, sanitation, and hygiene program cycle in northern Uganda?
- II. What are the institutional constraints on the participation of disabled people the design and implementation of the WASH agenda in Gulu District in Northern Uganda?
- III. What are the capacity constraints on the participation of disabled people in the design and implementation of the WASH agenda in Gulu District in Northern Uganda?
- IV. In what ways does the quality of inter-organizational relationships between key stakeholders affect the implementation of the WASH agenda amongst disabled people?
- V. What needs to be done differently in institutional development terms to ensure the equitable participation of disabled people in the design and implementation of the WASH agenda in district in Gulu District?
- VI. What kinds of capacities are needed to allow greater participation by disabled people and how might these be built?

A qualitative approach was used to collect data from participants representing the target population of Gulu District. Data was collected through Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), A total of 4 FGDs, and 5 KIIs were conducted. Data was collected with team from Gulu disabled persons Union and some members from subcounty association of disabled persons. All interviews and FGDs were audio recorded and transcribed thereafter. Analysis was done using Atlas Ti. A social ecological model and critical disability theory was used in the analysis to understand institutional and capacity constraints on inclusion of disabled people in the WASH agenda.

Key Findings

The findings from the study were institutional, attitudinal and physical barriers to WASH inclusion and are summarised as follows;

Institutional barriers

- There is power relations challenges among leaders of disabled persons and members of the communities.

- Inadequate data for people with disabilities in Gulu. This stems from non-inclusive data collection and reporting tool being used by the local government.
- Limited planning and budgeting for people with disability especially at subcounty and district level.
- There is limited capacity to provide for disability friendly WASH facilities at various institutions.
- There is coordination and communication challenge especially with development actors and local government.
- There is inadequate feedback and accountability mechanism to people with disabilities especially at community and household level.

Physical Barriers

- WASH facilities designs do not favor people with disability both at institutional and household level in Gulu.
- Long distances to WASH facilities and to meetings venues is a challenge to people with disabilities.
- Most people with disabilities do not have assisting devices such as wheelchairs, guiding sticks, brails among others, and that has affected their access to WASH services.

Attitudinal barriers.

- There is discrimination against people with disabilities in communities more that at household and local government level.
- People with disability have self-pity and tend to shy away from WASH services because they feel they do not add value in the society.
- Many people with disability do not know their rights to WASH services.

Coping mechanism

- People with disability seek support to WASH services from family members and people of good will in the communities.
- Many improvise to cope with limited access to WASH services, some defecate in open bushes behind their homes when the latrines are unhygienic or not there at all, some access water from nearby ponds

Recommendations

There is need to address institutional, physical and attitudinal barriers to disability inclusion in WASH and coping mechanism supported.

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Chapter 1

1.1 Aim and objectives of the Study

The overall aim of the study is to explore the institutional and capacity constraints on the inclusion of people with disability in water, sanitation, and hygiene services in Gulu district, in northern Ugandan context. The investigation will involve people with disability in rural communities of northern Uganda, some members of disabled person's organisations (DPOs) and local authorities.

1.2 Specific objectives:

1. ***To explore the key sanitation and hygiene issues being faced by people with disability in Northern Uganda.***

Under this objective, the study will determine the key water, sanitation and hygiene issues experienced at individual, household, community, and policy level.

2. ***To understand the nature of the bias / discrimination being faced by people with disability.***

To achieve this objective, the study will use the social ecological model to understand different ways in which bias is manifested in the access to sanitation and hygiene facilities/services. This will involve exploring the inclusion biases at each of the social ecological model (individual, household or network, community, and policy levels). In addition, the study will also look at positive behavior (positive deviance) that has been adopted by community members facing similar discrimination to successfully find strategies and behaviors that enable them to find better solutions to problems than their peers, while having access to the same resources and facing similar or worse challenges. In addition, the study shall also explore power relations, to understand who is responsible for the discrimination in access to water and sanitation for people with disability .

3. ***To explore coping mechanisms of people with disability on water sanitation and hygiene.***

Under this objective, the study will explore different levels of coping with social exclusion from access to water, sanitary and hygiene facilities/services. The levels include individual, household and community levels. Different individuals, communities and authorities are

expected to have different mechanisms of dealing with social inclusion, based on their cultural, social, economic, structural and policy circumstances.

Chapter 2

2.1 Introduction and Background

Access to safe water, good sanitation and hygiene is paramount for human survival and dignity. According to UNITED NATIONS GENERAL ASSEMBLY (2010) water, sanitation, and hygiene is a basic human right and should be accessed by all. To date, not all human population have access to safe drinking water, sanitation, and hygiene. At global level, one in three people do not have access to safe drinking water, two out of five people do not have a basic hand-washing facility with soap and water. Up to 2.3 billion people still lack access to basic sanitation and it is estimated that more than 673 million people still practice open defecation globally (WHO/UNICEF, 2017 and UN, 2019). Access to basic sanitation coverage in rural Uganda is at 79% and hand washing facilities is at 36.5% only (SPR, 2019). Even though Sustainable Development Goal 6 aims at universal access to water and sanitation, the last mile population being marginalised groups and people with disability either have limited or no access to suitable water, sanitation, and hygiene services. There is a considerable number of people who are disabled. According to World bank (2001), the estimated number of people with disability globally is 580 million and two thirds live in low-income countries of the South. Up to 70-80 percent of the disabled people live in rural areas (Hadiwigeno, 1999). In Uganda, the prevalence rate of disability among population from age of five years and above is 13.6 percent with highest form of disability being difficulty seeing (6.5% of the population), difficulty remembering (5.4%); difficulty walking (4.5%); and difficulty hearing (3.1%) (UBOS,2016).

People with disability are vulnerable by virtue of their impairment and negative societal attitudes arising from fear, ignorance, superstitions, neglect, and lack of awareness. As a result, they are deprived off access to services, information, resources as well as participation in the socio-economic development process. Consequently, the majority depend on their families and communities for survival.

Globally several countries have begun to recognize the rights of persons with disabilities by ratifying and acceding to the convention on the rights of persons with disability (CRPD). CRPD and as international law convention stipulates that at bare minimum, people with disability should be more visible before the law and that they should benefit from the 'rule of law' and that national legislations should align with the purpose of CRPD (UN, 2007). This law resonates with other international treaties and three qualities that define human rights as;

universal, inherent (“All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights”) and inalienable that human rights automatically belong to each human being (UN General Assembly,1948). According UN (2007) there are other specific international laws and conventions that have provision for related to protection of rights of persons with disabilities and they include;

- ILO Convention concerning Vocational Rehabilitation and Employment (Disabled Persons)
- Inter-American Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities
- Convention on the Rights of the Child (article 23);
- African Charter of Human and People's Rights (art. 18(4));
- the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child (article 13);
- European Social Charter (article 15); and
- Protocol of San Salvador (Additional Protocol to the American Convention on Human Rights in the Area of Economic, Social and Cultural Rights) (article 6 & 9)

In Uganda, there are several supportive policies such as the Constitution of Uganda, (1995). Article 21 which prohibits discrimination against people with disabilities, the Persons with Disabilities Act, (2019), which makes provisions for the elimination of all forms of discriminations against people with disabilities and towards equal opportunities, the National Council for Disability Act (No. 14), (2003), which monitors and evaluates the rights of persons with disabilities as set out in international conventions and legal instruments, the equal Opportunity Act, 2006, and the Employment Act (No. 6), (2006), both prohibit discrimination of persons in employment based on disability. the Universal Primary Education Act, makes it financially possible for families to send their disabled children to school by providing free primary education to four children in every family, including disabled children, and National Policy on Disabilities, (2006), that provides a human rights-based framework for responding to the needs of persons with disabilities and others.

Several scholars have developed theories and concepts considering social change processes related to disability and inclusion. The critical disability theory for instance, advocate for an analysis of disability as a cultural, historical, relative, social and a political phenomenon (Meekosha & Shuttleworth 2009; Vehmas & Watson 2014). The theory suggests structuring of institutions, social identities, cultural practices, political positions, historical communities, and shared human experience of embodiment. Similarly, the social model suggest that disability is a socially constructed phenomenon. Societies or communities tend to segregate or discriminate people with disability because they are different. In northern Uganda for

instance, people with disability are named according to their impairment for example 'Ojok or Ajok' which means ghost or out cast. Barnes & Mercer et al (2010) argue that it is society 'which disables people with impairments, and therefore any meaningful solution must be directed at societal change rather than individual adjustment and rehabilitation.' Understanding the environment, stakeholders, relationships, and power relation is important when advocating for disability inclusion. The social ecological model provides clear knowledge on interrelations among individuals and environmental influence (Golden & Earp,2012). The model suggests that social change in society can be achieved through interaction, partnership and doing no harm and empowering the most vulnerable members of societies. Social inclusion may be advanced by reducing the opportunity gap and by creating an enabling environment for people with disability to participate more equitably. Building social inclusion involves activities for increasing equal participation in processes that improve well-being, that shape equal freedom and room for people to pursue their own development. It is crucial to understand the social construction of disability to engage with the process of eradicating barriers and to pave way for inclusive practice to minimise disadvantage. According to Goujon, N., & Devine, A., et al (2014) inclusive practice needs to be embedded in institutions' routine practices. Disability inclusive development programs should promote improved participation of people with disabilities in their communities, such as improved access to education, health services and meaningful employment and contributing to an overall improvement in the quality of life of people within their societies. It begins with awareness creation and ensuring that there is a disability friendly environment.

This study seeks to explore and understand the institutional and capacity constraints on inclusion of disabled people in the WASH agenda, the challenges experienced with a view to learning lessons to inform probable interventions that can be undertaken in Gulu District in northern Uganda.

Chapter 3

3.1 Problem Definition

Whilst there is increasing recognition that the needs of people with disability must be addressed by development and humanitarian interventions, it is also recognised that it is not always easy to achieve. Inclusion of people with disability remains a challenge. Uganda has had its fair but complex share in fronting disability inclusion. In the whole of sub-Saharan Africa, Uganda has been praised for advocating for the rights of people with disabilities. According to Ochom & Mannan (2014) the rights of people with disability have been included in the legal frame of Uganda and there has been a strong training focus on Community Based Rehabilitation (CBR) programmes established since 1992 under the Ministry of Gender, Labour and Social Development. CBR programme uses a multisectoral approach and the main activities include capacity building, economic empowerment, increasing disability awareness, disability management and home based care (Claussen, Kandyomunda & Jareg 2005; Norad 2011:87). However, there are gaps in laws, policies and practice in disability inclusion in Uganda. Specifically, these gaps are linked to negative cultural attitudes towards disability, poor funding, inadequate training in inclusive education and limited access to accessible information and assistive mobility devices. According to NPA (2017) there is inadequate disability data for effective planning. The general absence of data and statistics on disability is considered responsible for its reduced significance in programming and resource allocation. Secondly financial and human resources are not adequately aligned to meet the disability challenge. Additionally, the multi-sectoral coordination for disability and development is weak. All these challenges are barriers that lead to exclusion of persons with disabilities in all development interventions including WASH.

There are several barriers that people with disability face in accessing WASH services. Groce et al (2011) lists potential barriers to WASH among persons with disabilities in the spheres of technical access barriers (such as facility structure and distance to facilities), social barriers related to stigma or abuse, and communication barriers. Additionally, Wapling & Downie, (2012) further confirms that there are institutional barriers in form of laws, inadequate data on disability, policies, strategies, or practices that discriminate against people with disabilities. With all the barriers facing people with disability, it is crucial to understand the social construction of disability to engage with the process of eradicating barriers and to pave way for inclusive practice to minimise disadvantage. Inclusive practice needs to be embedded in institutions' routine practices.

3.2 Literature review

Understanding disability is complex because it is multidimensional and a contested concept. This presents a challenge in development management practice since people with disability are part of community where social change process happens. Inclusion of people with disability is crucial in development intervention especially in water sanitation and hygiene (WASH). However, inclusion of people with disability in WASH is hindered by several barriers. The barriers to disability inclusion may be categorized as attitudinal, environmental, institutional that work against the participation of people with disabilities (Rohwerder, 2015).

Disability inclusive responses aim at removing these barriers to enable equitable social change processes in communities. Addressing the different barriers, require a critical analysis of the power relations, good governance, inter-organisational relationship and ensuring that there is no harm to people with disability. Several scholars have developed theories and concepts considering social change processes related to disability and inclusion. The critical disability theory for instance, advocates for an analysis of disability as a cultural, historical, relative, social and a political phenomenon (Meekosha & Shuttleworth 2009; Vehmas & Watson 2014). The theory suggests the structuring of institutions, social identities, cultural practices, political positions, historical communities, and shared human experience of embodiment is important and necessary. Similarly, the social model suggest that disability is a socially constructed phenomenon. Societies or communities tend to segregate or discriminate against people with disability because they are different. In northern Uganda for instance, people with disability are named according to their impairment for example 'Ojok or Ajok' which means ghost or out cast. Barnes & Mercer et al (2010) argue that it is society 'which disables people with impairments, and therefore any meaningful solution must be directed at societal change rather than individual adjustment and rehabilitation.' Considering the complexity surrounding disability inclusion in WASH services, as Thomas (1996) puts it, 'managing the different interest, values, and goals' of those with power is challenging for development managers. Negotiation and brokering can be employed with a view to finding 'room for maneuver' in moving the inclusivity agenda forward. It is interesting to note that the social model seems to focus more on collective action towards disability inclusion and yet any behavior begins with an individual. In one way or the other, the current approach may to some extent ~~may~~ be causing harm to individuals with disability because by virtue of their lack of influence as to decision made in their name, individuals might accept any intervention not because they have a say, but because the group has decided. Their level of influence in the community is low on decision making. Empowerment and participation of individual persons with disability is therefore critical to their quality of life and consideration on the impact of disability on individuals is paramount (Al Ju'beh, 2015, p. 83-86; Rimmerman, 2013, p. 30).

The social ecological model conceptualizes interrelations among individuals and environmental influences (Golden & Earp,2012). The model suggests that social change in society can be achieved through interaction, partnership, doing no harm and empowering the most vulnerable members of societies. Social change should therefore involve social inclusion. Social inclusion may be advanced by closing the opportunity gap and by creating an enabling environment for people with disability to participate more equitably. This process may involve interaction with different actors and as such, relationship building with different institution and organisations is critical. For instance in Uganda some of the organisations that work together in disability inclusion are; national union of persons with disability organisation (NUDIPO), local government community based services department at District level, ministry of gender, labour and social development, private sector and non-organisations (Abimanyi-Ochom & Mannan , 2014). The challenge that can be experienced with actors, could be linked to coordination, values, varying interest and goals. A development practitioner should therefore identify the boundary of interaction and negotiation.

Building social inclusion involves activities for increasing equal participation in processes that improve well-being, that shape equal freedom and room for people to pursue their own development. Much as there is need for equality in disability inclusion, equity cannot be ignored. According to White et al (2016) development practitioners involved in WASH disability inclusion or mainstreaming should focus on achieving equitable rather than equal WASH services access. This may require thinking beyond adaptive technologies to include community support and hygiene promotion tailored to specific needs. Understanding the consequences of non-compliance with WASH standards for disabled people provides important context to this issue. It can inform broader agenda setting by highlighting the measurable impact that inaccessible or unacceptable WASH has on the lives of disabled people and the wider community including its association with productivity, disease transmission and self-esteem. Inclusive practice therefore needs to be embedded in institutions' routine practices. It begins with awareness creation and ensuring that there is a disability friendly environment.

3.3 Research questions

After critical review of written academic and grey materials and interaction with development practitioners with experience in water sanitation and hygiene (WASH), the following research questions were generated to guide investigation on disability inclusion in WASH services in northern Uganda.

1. To what extent are people with disability at community level involved in water, sanitation, and hygiene program cycle in northern Uganda?
2. What are the institutional constraints on the participation of disabled people the design and implementation of the WASH agenda in Gulu District in Northern Uganda?
3. What are the capacity constraints on the participation of disabled people in the design and implementation of the WASH agenda in Gulu District in Northern Uganda?
4. In what ways does the quality of inter-organizational relationships between key stakeholders affect the implementation of the WASH agenda amongst disabled people?
5. What needs to be done differently in institutional development terms to ensure the equitable participation of disabled people in the design and implementation of the WASH agenda in district in Gulu District?
6. What kinds of capacities are needed to allow greater participation by disabled people and how might these be built?

Chapter 4

4.1 Methodology and Research Design

4.2 Methodology

This section present methodological components of the study. It focuses on research design, population and sample size, data collection and analysis.

4.3 Research Design

Research design is useful for planning and conducting a study or investigation to obtain intended results and increasing chances of getting information that can be linked to real situation. This investigation was carried out in four villages of Lakwela, Te-olam, Laminto and corner ward in Paicho sub county, Gulu District, in Northern Uganda as summarized in table 1.

Table 1: Study site, Number of FGD respondents and interviewers

S/No	Parish	Village Name	Number participants / Respondents for focused group discussion	Number co-facilitators from GDIPU and Subcounty disabled persons elected leaders	Sex/ Gender	
					Male	Female
1	Kal Ali	Laminto	11	2	6	7
2	Kal Ali	Corner Ward	13	3	9	7
3	Kal Ali	Te-olam	13	1	7	7
4	Kal Ali	Lakwela	12	3	6	9
Total			49	9	28	30

A qualitative approach was used to gather data from participants representing the target population of Gulu District in Northern Uganda. Qualitative data was collected through two methods, namely Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) with disabled persons organisations (DPOs), subcounty disabled persons association, elected leaders, local government officers at district and subcounty level, WASH practitioner from world vision and secondly through Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with people with disability. To gather shared meaning, different perspectives, value judgment and to aid triangulation on disability inclusion in WASH. Up to 58 respondents were covered by the data collection process as summarised in table 2.

Table 2: Summary of Target Respondents.

S/No	Respondent category	Institution	Number / members
1	Focused group discussion members	Community / village	47
2	Key informants	Gulu disabled persons Union (GUDIPU)	3
		Local government officers (District and Subcounty)	3
		Subcounty disabled persons association at subcounty level	2
		WASH practitioner from World vision	1
		Elected leaders (Disabled persons representatives)	2
Total			58

4.4 Sampling methods

Sampling in qualitative studies differs fundamentally from quantitative approaches. Stratified sampling was used to target people with disability in Paicho sub county. To select the participants within the study area for focused group discussion, a multi-stage sampling procedure was used to critically identify the respondents without 'doing harm'. The subcounty disabled persons association, the local government community development officer was engaged to support in identification and mobilisation of the respondents at parish level. Selection criteria for the FGD include used were as follows:

- Selection of the parish and villages was informed by data from Gulu disabled persons' union and Gulu district community-based services department.
- As a result of COVID 19 pandemic restrictions one parish with high number of people with different types disability namely physical, visual, sensory, hearing and intellectual was selected.
- On average 12 participants were selected for the four villages as summarised in table 1.
- Each focused group discussion had both men and women as indicated in table 1.
- Some people with disability accompanied by their care takers and transport provision arranged.

4.5 Data collection process

In preparation to kick start data collection, four villages and their meeting venues were identified and all necessary logistics like transport refunds to persons with disabilities and their care takers were arranged. Additionally, a revision of the focused group discussion questions was done in consultation with the tutor see annex 1. The revision included alignment to the overarching research question and narrowing down the study location to only Paicho subcounty in Gulu District. Before the actual data collection, a pretest of both focused group discussion and key informants interview tools were carried out. The pre-test informed decision to mobilize to a greater extent all types of disabilities to ensure that there is good representation and response to the questions without bias based on interviewer's world views on disability. As Anderson (1999) argues, development action should not be seen to cause harm to the beneficiaries. To ensure that no harm is caused during the interview and to boost self-esteem and get proper response, a language interpreter, representative from Gulu disabled persons union and subcounty representative for persons with disabled supported to administer some questions during focused group discussion in the selected villages.

Figure 1: Emma Akello Gulu disabled persons union staff recording response from FGD participant.

Care was taken to ensure that the officials invited to support the investigation did not influence participants responses and views. This was done by holding the discussion

in community meeting areas (in a central place within the villages), creating good rapport and ensuring that we listened more to the participants.

To encourage participation and reduce dominant characters in the focused group discussion, participants were given equal opportunities to speak freely, further probing and repeating the questions especially where there seems to be some power relations and biases was done. As Gerhard (2008) argues, when carrying out an investigation, it is crucial not to be biased if one is to understand and gain knowledge on the problem being investigated. This argument resonates with Thomas (1996) argument of ensuring that any intervention aimed at social change should take into consideration conflicts of goals, values, and interests. Similarly, care was taken to ensure there is cultural sensitivity before and during the discussion. This was informed by the pre test done prior to the focused group discussion. Checkland (2000) argues that culture can influence and impact on any intervention and therefore it is worth while for development practitioners to have a clearing analysis and knowledge about culture due to social roles, rules of engagement or norms, values, identity and power play that it has within a social setting.

Due to the impact of COVID 19 pandemics, clearance from local authorities to engage people with disabilities in the communities was sought and varying dates for focused group discussion in the selected four (4) villages was set. Using key informant interview questions in annex 3, a total of five key informants' interviews were conducted with coordinator of Gulu disabled persons union, Paicho subcounty community development officer, Gulu District community development officer in charge of people with disabilities ,Gulu District community development officer and world vision.

Figure 2. GDPU Leaders and Key informants

4.6 Data Processing

As stated above, data was collected through KIIs and FGDs. All the interviews and discussions were recorded, and notes were taken too. The digital recordings were transcribed, translated, and typed in English. See annex 2 for sample transcript.

The two data collection tools developed assessed and provided understanding of the institutional and capacity constraints on inclusion of people with disabilities in WASH services, challenges and lessons that can inform probable intervention in Gulu District.

4.7 Data Analysis

After completion of data collection, the transcribed audio recording and notes taken, was transferred to Atlas Ti analysis software, and analysis was done. Prior to the analysis, coding of key themes linked to the research questions, theories, concepts, and reviewed literature related to disability inclusion WASH was done. According to Bryman (2012) to easily identify key themes in transcribed documents, coding makes it easy for qualitative data to be broken down into their component parts. Therefore, after coding, a full list of themes was identified for categorization within a hierarchical framework of main and sub-themes. The overarching questions generated for this investigation was used as a yard stick for coding and identification of the key themes.

The thematic framework was then systematically applied to all the interview transcripts and typed notes. Patterns and associations of the themes was identified and compared within and between the different groups of respondents both focused groups and key informants to enhance triangulation of data. Triangulation simply means use of several methods or data sources in qualitative research to develop a comprehensive understanding of phenomena (Patton 1999). The two methods used was meant to capture data on how people with disability identify themselves within their community, relationship with their families, community, and local governments, the interorganisational relationships especially how they cooperate, communicate to each other, coordination mechanism and point of emergence especially among the different institutions and actors in disability inclusion WASH.

4.8 Reflection on the Methodology

The investigation in the selected villages and with key informants went on successfully amidst interruption by restriction due to COVID 19 increase in community transmission in northern Uganda. The initial plan was to use 20 days for data collection but that was not possible. One of the coping mechanisms adopted was to begin with key informants' interview as clearance to engage the community members in focused group discussion was pending approval by local authorities. One big success was the involvement of disability representatives from Gulu district disabled person's union and a member of subcounty disabled persons association in the focused group discussion. Their presences in the meetings boosted participants self-esteem and responses. All respondents participated actively in the discussions.

The two tools used for data collection i) focused group discussion and ii) key informant interviews have their own strengths and weaknesses. For instance, focused group discussion involves a number of participants having an open discussion on a specific topic, set by a researcher. The researcher acts as a moderator or facilitator to aid discussion by using probes to collect desirable data which is often recorded, and transcripts are used to interpret and analyse given information. Usually the interaction presents opportunity to the investigation to check their own world views and their values, hence learning. The emotional connection can be achieved once good rapport and biases is avoided as much as possible. However, the interactive, dynamic aspect of the focus group discussion method can be limiting or liability because physical proximity of participants during the discussion can unleash several factors that can threaten data quality if left unchecked. For instance, fear due power dynamics between investigation and the respondents and dominant individuals in the group. According to Roller & Lavrakas, (2015) one of the most important factors is the calibre of the discussion; specifically, the extent to which all participants have a fair chance of voicing their input. This is critical because the success of the group discussion method hinges on generating a true discussion where everyone present participates in a dialogue with the other group members and, to a lesser

degree, with the moderator. Additionally, the interviewer bias, training in the in-depth interviewing method, and how the moderator manages the group interaction affects the direction of the outcomes.

The key informants' interviews on the other hand has its strengths and weakness. Key informant's key informant interviews often provide data and insight that cannot be obtained with other methods. confidential information that would not be released in other settings. This was true especially when it came to access to some finances given to groups persons with disability in Paicho subcounty. During the focused group discussion participants in some villages did not mention any thing related to access to financial support from the government. The other strength is that it easier to identify and interview key informants because they are in most cases informed and are within reach for instance Gulu district disabled persons union and other local government offices had some data though not adequate about disability in the entire district. With COVID 19 interference Key informants became very important in providing relevant information about WASH disability inclusion and guide on feasible approach to get participants in villages with the restriction in place. However, there are limitation with key informants that can not ignored. For instance, key informant interviews provide only a very limited basis and may bias the investigation outcome if not complimented with other tools. Therefore, a combination of tools is important for triangulation and to reducing biases.

4.9 Limitation of the Study

This study collected only qualitative data. While the study explored institutional and capacity constraints on inclusion of disabled people in the WASH agenda and its challenges in Paicho subcounty in Gulu District in northern Uganda, the extent of constraints and the challenges can not be quantitatively established using qualitative data. This study did not include control individual or group people without disability. Ideally this group may have some contribution to the outcome of the investigation since they are part of the communities where the persons with disability live.

Another limitation is boundary of the investigation which was WASH disability inclusion and associated challenges but there was limited focus on best practices at difference institution. Future investigation could incorporate a quantitative survey to establish magnitude of disability inclusion in WASH at the different institutions and be able to identify best practices that can be replicated.

Chapter 5

5.1 Findings

5.2 Data analysis and preliminary findings

This section of the report presents the key findings of the study. The findings are based on the overarching research questions which is linked to the research objective. The emerging findings from the analysis shows that the institutional and capacity constraints on inclusion of people with disability in the WASH agenda is physical, institutional, and attitudinal. These barriers is presented as follows:

5.3 Institutional barriers

The focused group discussion and key informants interview provided opportunity to investigate institutional barriers at family, community, disabled persons organisation (Gulu disabled persons union and subcounty disabled association) and local government institutions.

The investigation revealed that there are power relations challenges among leaders of disabled persons and members of the communities. The leaders normally do not have enough authority and power to implement different laws and policies on disability inclusion. One of the reasons stated was that communities think they are powerless since they have disability. The appreciation of the contribution of persons with disability in the community is still minimal. Failure to recognise the contribution of people with disability and the power they hold resonate with the Social model on disability which suggest that disability is a socially constructed phenomena where communities don't value contribution of persons with disability and critical disability theory which recognises the influence of social identity, cultural practices political positions and history of the community (Meekosha & Shuttleworth 2009; Vehmas & Watson 2014). During the focused group discussion in Te-olam village the subcounty elected leader in the council stated that much as there are the policies and good laws in Uganda on disability inclusion the implementation is a problem. *"we are just occupying this office, our contribution in enforcing the policies and laws on disability inclusion is also disabled by the community. We still have a long way to go"*.

The finding revealed that there is inadequate data on the number people with disabilities and types of disability in Gulu. This stems from non-inclusive data collection and reporting tool being used by the local government. According to the community development officer in charge persons with disability in Gulu district, there is no comprehensive data on disability. At the moment reliable data can be obtained from Gulu disabled persons union and world vision.

There is limited planning and budgeting for people with disability especially at subcounty and district level. The planning cycle in the local government in Uganda involves participatory and joint planning right from villages spearheaded by the parish development committees, at subcounty level by the technical planning committees up to district level. However, it emerged that little attention is put to budget and plan for water, sanitation, and hygiene services for people with disabilities. The fund appropriation is meagre towards disability inclusion due to limited data on the number and types of disability and low prioritisation by the approvers (political leaders). Even though there is a special fund for people with disability from the central government, it rarely reaches all the people with disabilities. Only few organised groups of people with disabilities have access this fund. In Kal Ali parish where the investigation was carried out only one group is benefiting from this fund. According to NPA (2017) the local governments have been encouraged to mainstream disability inclusion in WASH because the current financial and human resources are not adequately aligned to meet the disability challenge.

There is limited capacity to provide for disability friendly WASH facilities at various institutions. Even though some public places like banks, markets, health units, schools have accessible WASH facilities, not all are up to expected standards to enable chain of access. According CBM (2016) design of WASH facility should provide easy access by person with disability. The coordinator of Gulu disabled person stated that much as most institutions in Gulu have adopted universal design of WASH infrastructure, access to these facilities is still a challenge because they are not designed to standard. Through the discussion it became clear that there need for reasonable accommodation in the WASH facilities. In other words, need to adjust the current WASH facilities at institution to become WASH friendly.

There is coordination and communication challenge especially with development actors and local government. Gulu district has a vibrant district water and sanitation coordination committee platform that seats every quarter to discuss WASH issues, however issues of disability inclusion in WASH services rarely features in the meetings. It is expected that since there are disabled persons elected and technical leaders at district and subcounty level, communication flow would be adequate up to community level. However, that is not the case, participants interviewed stated that they normally do not get information or do not get in time. Similarly, much as there is efforts by Gulu disabled persons union, World Vision and Humanity International, SNV and USAID to coordinate and cooperation on disabilities matters, not all

relevant development actors get involved in disability WASH inclusion platforms. There is a claim that at times their participation is hindered by project designs and donor restrictions in some of the intervention issues. According to World Vision projects in WASH that are not inclusive enough and participation in disability inclusion meetings may not add value for such projects.

According to focused group discussions there is inadequate feedback and accountability mechanisms to people with disabilities especially at community and household level. One respondent stated that;

“ we have become, a learning sample for many actors, they come gather our views and fail to give us feedback or even account for money they receive on our behalf and yet they do not know that ; any thing for us, without us, is not ours”

5.4 Physical Barriers

The emerging findings from focused group discussions and key informants' interviews revealed that WASH facilities designs do not favor people with disabilities both at institutional and household level in Gulu. According to NPA (2017) institutions should frequently carry out accessibility audits so that reasonable accommodations are done. People with disabilities share the same facilities which are often not hygienic especially for persons who are crippled, hence limiting access. **Figure 2:**

Figure 3: Shared Household Latrine in Laminto village, Paicho Subcounty Gulu District.

During the focused group discussion and key informants' interview, it merged that most people with disabilities do not have assisting devices such as wheelchairs, guiding sticks, brails among others, and that has affected their access to WASH services. Access to some of the facilities becomes a challenge to persons with disability because they are simply not friendly.

The study revealed that long distances to WASH facilities and to meetings venues is a challenge to people with disabilities. During planning for the WASH facilities at subcounty and village level not much consideration is put cater for persons with disabilities. Water points are not designed with ramps and at times is far away from the dwelling of persons with disability.

5.5 Attitudinal barriers

The finding reveals that there is discrimination against people with disabilities in communities more that at household and local government level. One of the reasons is that community members consider people with disabilities as curse or outcaste in the community and have no

value. Majority of community members do not involve them regularly in WASH interventions because some think they have no contribution.

Secondly many community members do not know how to handle the needs of people with disabilities. See figure 4.

Figure 4: Disabled child isolated in hut that he shares with goats, in Corner Ward village, Paicho Sub county Gulu District

People with disability have self-pity and tend to shy away from WASH services because they feel they do not add value in the society. The self-pity was detected during the focused group discussion. When asked whether they knew their rights to WASH services some participants did not know and mentioned that is the government to support them access the services.

Cultural beliefs on disability are still negative. Communities tend not to provide for the persons with disabilities and wish for their death. Those with severe disabilities are neglected most and at times abandoned. They are treated differently from other peoples. The neglect has greatly reduced their lifespan. People believe that some disabilities spread when one gets into contact with the impaired person and most especially epilepsy. The victim is abandoned once they are under attack with epilepsy. This causes stigma and affects their access to WASH services.

5.6 Coping mechanism

The study findings show that much as there are barriers to access to WASH services by persons with disability, people with disability seek support to WASH services from family members and people of good will in the communities. The support comes in the form of construction of latrines for persons with disability, fetching water and even bathing those who are not able to clean themselves.

Figure 5: Pit Latrine dug by Sons of Akidi Elvarina (person with disability)

Many improvise to cope with limited access to WASH services, some defecate in open bushes behind their homes when the latrines are unhygienic or not there at all, some access water from nearby ponds. Figure 6:

Figure 6: Drinking water source mainly used by Disabled person. Mr. Okello in Corner ward village Paicho Sub county Gulu District.

The association of persons with disabilities who have members up to village level often try to lobby and advocate for services including WASH from local government and development partners through their DPO (Gulu disabled persons union and elected councilors) even though little is done according to the discussion but there is increasing awareness about the needs of person with disabilities. However, this is a political process that requires a lot of interaction and negotiations.

There are disabled persons savings and loan associations that help them address some of their WASH access challenges like construction of latrines and hand washing facilities and face masks for prevent possible COVID 19 infection. “Ribe aye teko” (Unity is strength) village savings and loan association in Te-olam village is one of the groups have active savings and loan association comprising mainly persons with disability. This group is partly also benefiting from special funds for people disability in Kal Ali parish, Paicho subcounty.

Chapter 6:

6.1 Conclusion,

The emerging preliminary results from the investigation show that there are basically three main barriers to WASH access by persons with disability in Paicho subcounty, Gulu district and they include: physical linked to inaccessible WASH facilities long distance to water services, and institutional barriers which is related to limited implementation of laws and policies on disability inclusion, inadequate data on the type and number of persons with disability and inadequate planning and budgeting for disability WASH inclusion interventions; the attitudinal barriers where the study found out that people with disabilities in the study sites face multiple marginalization arising from cultural and social construct or norms especially by community members. For instance, they have inadequate access to information, services, rarely participate in meetings, capacity building and other development programmes, and they have limited opportunities to earn an income. All these exclusions aggravate their poor access to and effective use of water, sanitation, and hygiene facilities and services. Even though all these barriers have been impacting on access to WASH services, persons with disabilities developed coping mechanism such as seeking supporting from family members and people of good will, lobby and advocacy through their association and participating in village savings and local associations.

6.2 Recommendations

- The attitudinal barriers especially at community level as highlighted by Barnes & Mercer et al (2010) that it is society 'which disables people with impairments, and that meaningful solution must be directed at societal change rather than individual adjustment and rehabilitation.' Can be addressed through integration and inclusion of people with disabilities in water sanitation and hygiene interventions at communities and institutional level. Currently due to limited human and financial resources to address disabilities issues, the government of Uganda is encouraging mainstreaming of disabilities services (NPA 2017). From key informants' interview this is feasible because during mainstreaming little is done for persons with disabilities to improve WASH services access. Therefore, inclusion and integration of peoples with disabilities in WASH intervention. What is termed as the twin track approach.
- Local leaders should rekindle the community helping spirit and mobilize community members to help persons with disabilities to construct sanitation facilities such as latrines and hand washing facilities. This strategy is cheaper, rooted in the traditional social norms of the community, and more likely to be sustainable.

- Local government authorities should enforce policies and bylaws on people with disability friendly latrines / toilets in public places and institutions. This enforcement can begin with awareness creation and understanding of the different policies and laws. Since Gulu district has an active DPO, they could use them to help disseminate the policies since they have capacity to locate and communicate with persons with disability in the district.
- Local government authorities should take more interest in conducting disability audits in institutions and public places and act on their findings to ensure availability of disability friendly facilities in such places.
- Local leaders and local government authorities should ensure more involvement of people with disability in planning and decision-making processes. This can easily be done through religious, cultural leaders, the subcounty associations and Gulu disabled persons union since there is still some stigmatisation in the communities
- Given the challenges posed by lack of access to safe water for the people with disabilities, local government and other partners should support rainwater harvesting for households with persons with disability.
- Innovations in technologies should include persons with disability friendly hand-pumps (for boreholes) and tippy taps to ensure that people with physical impairments are able to easily use these facilities.
- More advocacy to increase the involvement people with disabilities in planning, budgeting and decision-making processes and for the implementation of existing disability friendly policies.
- Ensure that there are indicators that explicitly address disability such as number of accessible WASH trainings and facilities. This could be supported by formative research and specifically using the Washington group question which asks question related to all types of disabilities namely; physical, visual, intellectual and sensory.
- There is need to improve on coordination and communication with development actors by the local government. Every quarter local government hold district water and sanitation coordination meetings however not all actors are invited to this meeting. According coordinator for GDPU, they rarely receive invitation for the meeting and yet they have enough advice to share with all development actors.

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Annex 1. Focused Group Discussion Questions

WASH Disability inclusion Study FGD Tool	
Moderator:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Thank you for coming to this discussion• My name isand my colleagues names are ... I am a student of the Open University of UK• Your opinion and views will be very helpful to us to establish the extent to which people with disability participate and have access to WASH services among community members in your area. This information will be useful for this study and to USAID / Sanitation for health activities project currently supporting your subcounty with WASH improvement. Your thoughts and ideas are important to us.• There are no right or wrong answers to our questions. Please feel free to express all of your ideas and opinions.• Any information that you provide will be considered private and confidential and will be used only for this research. Your name will not be used in any reports.• Your answers will be grouped with the answers of other participants and only your village, Parish, subcounty or district may be identified.• You are encouraged to participate in the discussion as much as possible. Your participation is voluntary. If you are not comfortable with a question, you may choose not to answer it. You may leave the discussion without penalty. You are free to ask questions at any time.• During the discussion we would like to use a recording device to facilitate note taking and to better capture what is being said. Members of the study team will only hear the recording.• During the discussion, the research team would like to take photographs of you for use in our report. Your name will not be used with any photos without your permission.• Before we start, do you have any questions?• During the discussion, please speak one at time so that everyone can hear what is being said.• If anyone has a mobile device, please turn it off or put it on silent mode• May I begin the session now?

1. Are people with disability both children and adults able to access all WASH services offered?
2. What are the challenges that you face in accessing WASH services in this area?
3. Do you think your community are aware or understand the needs people with disability?
4. Do you know of any intervention or initiative either by your community or other external actors that include people with disability in WASH services?
5. What kind meetings / events do the people with disability generally participate in?

6. Do people with disability participate, attend meetings, speak and influence decisions on water, Sanitation and Hygiene programmes
7. Are people with disability included and are actively involved in decision making process at household level, community and subcounty level?
8. What evidence can be given that people with disability have influenced decisions?
9. Are both men and women with disability treated equally or fairly in WASH service delivery?
10. If not why what could be the reason? Please explain.
11. Do people with disability have better understanding of their rights and entitlement in WASH?
12. How do people with disability cope with barriers in WASH services access in this area?
13. What do you recommend improving involvement and participation of people with disability in WASH intervention?

Annex 2: Sample Transcribed Data.

Focused Group Discussion Questions _ Lakwela village

WASH Disability inclusion Study FGD Tool
Moderator:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Thank you for coming to this discussion• My name is ... and my colleagues names are ... I am of the Open University of the United Kingdom• Your opinion and views will be very helpful to us to establish the extent to which people with disability participate and have access to WASH services among community members in your area. This information will be useful for this study and to USAID / Sanitation for health activities project currently supporting your subcounty with WASH improvement. Your thoughts and ideas are important to us.• There are no right or wrong answers to our questions. Please feel free to express all of your ideas and opinions.• Any information that you provide will be considered private and confidential and will be used only for this research. Your name will not be used in any reports.• Your answers will be grouped with the answers of other participants and only your village, Parish, subcounty or district may be identified.• You are encouraged to participate in the discussion as much as possible. Your participation is voluntary. If you are not comfortable with a question, you may choose not to answer it. You may leave the discussion without penalty. You are free to ask questions at any time.• During the discussion we would like to use a recording device to facilitate note taking and to better capture what is being said. Members of the study team will only hear the recording.• During the discussion, the research team would like to take photographs of you for use in our report. Your name will not be used with any photos without your permission.• Before we start, do you have any questions?• During the discussion, please speak one at time so that everyone can hear what is being said.• If anyone has a mobile device, please turn it off or put it on silent mode• May I begin the session now?

S/No	Questions	Response
1	Are people with disability both children and adults able to access all WASH services offered?	Not all can access.
2	What are the challenges that you face in accessing WASH services in this area?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Accessibility challenge to toilet and water facilities especially by the physically impaired individuals, the facilities are not disability friendly.- The toilet facilities are not always clean especially if shared with other members of the households.- Stigmatisation is common in communities and creates fear in accessing the WASH facilities.

3	Do you think your community are aware of or understand the needs people with disability?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not all understand the needs of people disability. But the few who do have no means of supporting people with disability. - There is still discrimination. " all are candidate of disability"
4	Do you know of any intervention or initiative either by your community or other external actors that include people with disability in WASH services? if yes name (it) them.	Yes, often people with disabilities are visited but there is very little support from external actors. There is little support from community members especially from people disability. People with disability in te kwela village majority don't have adequate sanitation and hygiene facilities
5	What kind of meetings / events do the people with disability generally participate in?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community meetings - Church meetings - WASH meetings - People with disability meetings organised by external actors. - Development meetings

6	What kinds of factors prevent or work against people with disability participating in the events/ meeting?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stigma from communities - Nature of disability - Long distance to meeting venues / transport challenges - Limited voice and decision from people with disability discourages them from participating. - Bad road condition and weather like rain that work against people with disabilities - Inadequate mobilisation of people with disabilities.
7	Do people with disability speak and influence decisions on water, Sanitation and Hygiene programmes?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They do speak but have little or no influence
8	What might be done to improve inclusion people with disability in these meetings and ensure their voices are heard?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supporting people with disability to speak openly and they should be recognised. - There should be recording voice of people with disability and played to leaders and communities to boost their self esteem - Mobilisation for meeting should be done in time and where possible should be through disabled persons elected leaders. - Meeting venue should be easily accessible and with disability friendly sanitation and hygiene facilities. -
9	Are people with disability included and are actively involved in decision making process at household level, community and subcounty level?	Yes though limited all the levels,

10	What evidence can be given that people with disability have influenced decisions?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are elected people with disability leaders from village to district level who try to raise challenges faced by people with disabilities. - There are nine groups of persons with disabilities in the whole of Paicho subcounty who have been supported with seed grants to carry out income generating activities but only one is group with only 10 people is from Kal Ali parish.
11	Are both men and women with disability treated equally or fairly in WASH service delivery?	Not common, women are more favoured.
12	If not why what could be the reason? Please explain.	It is not the same, women seems to be considered more by the nature of gender. Again it depends on the type of disability.

13	Do people with disability have better understanding of their rights and entitlement in WASH?	Not all are aware because not all attend and participate in meetings and trainings.
14	If, yes, in what ways?	<p>But the few who know there is understanding that WASH is health matter and everyone has right to health</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People with disability should be supported because they are more vulnerable to WASH diseases.
15	If not, why is this?	Limited participation in meeting and trainings where they get information.
16	How do people with disability cope with barriers in WASH services access in this area?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use family members to access WASH facilities. - Use money if they have. - Raise their voices through their elected leaders and group leaders

17	What are the outstanding challenges?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Poverty - Stigma from some of community members - Mobility challenge for physically impaired people. - Access to good sanitation and hygiene. - Health challenges due to some form of disability. - Long distances to social services like ; health facilities and water points.
18	What do you recommend improving involvement and participation of people with disability in WASH intervention?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provision of clean water services - Health facilities should be closer - Providing income generating activities for people with disabilities, especially in group. - Providing relief aid to people with disabilities - Proper coordination with the DPO in Gulu - Saving and loan association to boost income confidence and participation of all - Education on how to communicate and people with disabilities - Use elected and group leaders for people with disability. - Any planning and budgeting at subcounty should consider people with disability because “what is for us, without us, is not our”

19	<p>What kinds of capacities need to be built at the individual and organizational levels? How might these capacities be developed?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feedback mechanism of intervention to people with disability. - Income generating activities for organised group of people with disability. - Training other people in disability issues so that they understand. - Strengthening coordination from household to local government level. - Vocational training to people with disabilities in WASH and other development issues. - Support to appreciation of right of people with disability in WASH and all other aspect - Awareness creation about different type of disability and its challenges. - Availing water, sanitation and hygiene technologies that are disability friendly.

Annex 3. Key informant interview questions

WASH Disability inclusion Study KII Tool	
Moderator:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Thank you for coming to this discussion• My name is ... and my colleagues names are ... I am a student of the Open university of United Kingdom• Your opinion and views will be very helpful to us to establish the extent to which people with disability participate and have access to WASH services among community members in your area. This information will be useful for this study and to USAID / Sanitation for health activities project currently supporting your subcounty with WASH improvement. Your thoughts and ideas are important to us.• There are no right or wrong answers to our questions. Please feel free to express all of your ideas and opinions.• Any information that you provide will be considered private and confidential and will be used only for this research. Your name will not be used in any reports.• Your answers will be grouped with the answers of other participants and only your institution, may be identified.• You are encouraged to participate in the discussion as much as possible. Your participation is voluntary. If you are not comfortable with a question, you may choose not to answer it. You may leave the discussion without penalty. You are free to ask questions at any time.• During the discussion I intend use a recording device to facilitate note taking and to better capture what is being said. I will be the only one who will hear the recording.• During the discussion, I might take photographs of you for use in our report. Your name will not be used with any photos without your permission.• Before we start, do you have any questions? • May I begin the session now?

1. What data exists about people with disability in Gulu District?
 - How do NGO or government staff find out where people disabilities are living at the community level?

 - Is there any evidence about the situation of people with disabilities relating to access to WASH?

2. *What are the main barriers or challenges which prevent people with disabilities in Gulu from accessing WASH outcomes on an equal basis to others?*

3. How do people with disability cope with barriers in WASH services access in northern Uganda?

4. How do social norms, attitudes and beliefs relating to disability impact on people's access to WASH?

5. What approaches to WASH behaviors change or awareness raising have been used in Gulu?

6. What types of accessible WASH designs / technologies have been used in Gulu (both household level and public facilities)?
 - What do people with disabilities think of them (as end users)?

7. Are women, men and children with a disability directly involved in monitoring and evaluation activities?

8. Are WASH programs, including accessible infrastructure, embedded in institutions like schools, health facilities, marketplace, and places of worship?

9. What kinds of capacities are needed to allow greater participation by disabled people and how might these be built?

10. What are the capacity constraints on the participation of disabled people in the design and implementation of the WASH agenda in Gulu District in Northern Uganda?

11. In what ways does the quality of inter-organizational relationships (eg coordination, communication, healthy competition and cooperation) between key stakeholders affect the implementation of the WASH agenda amongst disabled people?

12. What needs to be done differently in institutional development terms to ensure the equitable participation of disabled people in the design and implementation of the WASH agenda in Gulu District?

13. What kinds of capacities are needed to allow greater participation by disabled people and how might these be built?